

ReMO Ambassador Programme: Becoming an ambassador for wellbeing in academia

Preparing your action plan: exercise booklet

As a ReMO Ambassador, you are committed to taking action at your local level. This booklet is full of questions and exercises that will help you to map out various elements pertaining to mental health in academia so you can design an action plan and identify priorities!

- Please identify associations, NGOs, non-profit organizations, businesses, communities that people struggling with mental health can talk to. These could be physical or digital.

C. Are support groups available in your country or institution? If yes, what could be an action to help them? If not, reflect on who/what organization would be the most appropriate to start one.

Step 2 – Moving stakeholders towards change

A. Please map out the stakeholders in your country.

Consider identifying Associations of universities, researchers, Unions, Ministries, Policy-makers, Institutions driving the mental health agenda as well as policies related to research careers etc.

For each, consider their motivation and agenda in terms of mental health. Try to identify their key past or current actions.

Then, identify those that can help you and those that you can help.

<i>Stakeholder</i>	<i>Motivation</i>	<i>Agenda</i>	<i>Key actions</i>	<i>Possible relationship to you (help you/them)</i>

B. Think of your situation. When it comes to taking action for mental health, what are the elements that give you:

- *Power to act:*

- *Legitimacy to act:*

- *Urgency to act:*

C. Think of your stakeholders. When it comes to taking action for mental health, which ones have

- *Power to act:*

- *Legitimacy to act:*

- *Urgency to act:*

D. Place them on the map. Now, which ones do you need to engage with, to monitor, to help, to inspire, to join etc.?

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E. Level of engagement: which stakeholders will you inform, consult, involve, collaborate, empower? Start thinking about WHAT you will be working on together

<i>Stakeholder</i>	<i>Inform</i>	<i>Consult</i>	<i>Involve</i>	<i>Collaborate</i>	<i>Empower</i>

F. How could you trigger change in your institution?

- What is the evidence telling you that something needs to change?
- What are the barriers to this change?
- What are the opportunities to trigger this change?
- Is this change something that should apply to other institutions?
- Do you need stakeholder support to achieve this change?
- Do you need to collect more evidence to achieve this change?

G. What is the powerful story you can tell to engage your stakeholders? Try to identify the rational and emotional elements you want to put forward for various stakeholders.

- Individual level:
- Institutional level:
- Policy level

Step 3 – Policy context

- A. Let's try to identify how the policy landscape is moving in terms of mental health
- Describe any national, federal, or regional legislation on mental health
 - Is mental health a topic of discussion in parliament? What is the conversation about and who drives it?
 - Describe the level of discussion among policy-makers of topics related to mental health in general population, workplace-specific, academia-specific.
 - Does the employer have a duty, by law, to ensure the mental health of workers?
 - Do national policies/ analogues of "Charter&Code" exist in the country? Do they have well-being or mental health recommendations in them? Are these policies or codes implemented and sanctioned?
 - Describe the role and place of trade unions, professional associations and organizations, which support researchers in the country

Are these rules criticized? Are they adequate to prevent potential mental health issues?

F. What types of statuses do PhD students/candidates typically have in your country?

G. Who has the power or interest to change something (concrete MPs, ministers, institutions, people in institutions)?

Step 5 – Action Plan

STRATEGY – Define what should be the overarching logic of your plan

PLAN – Planning ahead includes thinking about short-term, mid-term, and long-term. Consider actions that can be done within the next 6 months and actions that you will do at a later stage.

In any case, these actions should be executable.

<i>Objective</i>				
<i>Actions to undertake</i>				
<i>Who is your audience</i>				
<i>Who is your ally</i>				
<i>Who might be against your views</i>				
<i>What message will you deliver to your audience?</i>				
<i>How will you engage with stakeholders/allies?</i>				
<i>How will you consider those who might be against your views?</i>				
<i>What tools will you use to communicate?</i>				

<i>What support will you require from ReMO?</i>				
<i>How will you measure your success in implementing this action?</i>				
<i>Prioritize through time and identify links between the different actions you have in mind</i>				
<i>Deadline</i>				

Questions or suggestions?

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You can also join the ReMO Cost Action!

To learn more about what we do: <https://projects.tib.eu/remo/>